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Real-World Evidence on Prognostic Value of MRD in Multiple Myeloma Using Flow Cytometry

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ABSTRACT

Minimal residual disease (MRD) is one of the most important prognostic factors in multiple myeloma (MM) and a valid surrogate for progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS). Recently, MRD negativity was approved as an early clinical endpoint for accelerated drug approval in MM. Nevertheless, there is limited evidence of MRD utility in real-world setting. In this retrospective multicenter study, we report outcomes of 331 newly diagnosed MM patients with MRD evaluation at Day+100 after autologous stem cell transplantation using flow cytometry with a median limit of detection of 0.001%. MRD negativity was reached in 47% of patients and was associated with significantly prolonged median PFS (49.2 months vs. 18.4 months; hazard ratios (HR) = 0.37; $p < 0.001$) and OS (not reached vs. 74.9 months; HR = 0.50; $p = 0.007$). Achieving MRD negativity was associated with PFS improvements regardless of age, International Staging System (ISS) stage, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) level, or cytogenetic risk. Importantly, MRD positive patients benefited from lenalidomide maintenance versus no maintenance (18-months PFS: 81% vs. 46%; HR = 0.24; $p = 0.002$) while in MRD negative patients such benefit was not observed ($p = 0.747$). The outcomes of our real-world study recapitulate results from clinical trials including meta-analyses and support the idea that MRD positive patients profit more from lenalidomide maintenance than MRD negative ones.

Ludmila Muronova, Ondrej Soucek, and David Zihala contributed equally and are considered joint first authors.

[Correction added on 6 September 2025, after first online publication: The copyright line was changed.]

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1 | Introduction

Multiple myeloma (MM) is a genetically heterogeneous blood cancer characterized by the proliferation and accumulation of clonal plasma cells (PCs) in the bone marrow (BM), usually associated with the presence of monoclonal immunoglobulin in serum and/or urine. MM represents approximately 1% of all cancers and accounts for approximately 10% of hematologic malignancies [1]. During the last two decades, many novel treatment strategies have been implemented that translated into prolonged progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS) and lead to operational cure of subset of MM patients [2]. Hand in hand with therapeutic advances, majority of MM patients reach rapid and deep responses requiring novel approaches in response assessment. Conventional response evaluation in MM has relied dominantly on the kinetics of monoclonal immunoglobulin and free light chains in serum or urine [3]. The concept of minimal or measurable residual disease (MRD) has been adopted in many hematological malignancies and was officially implemented in International Myeloma Working Group (IMWG) updated response criteria in 2016 [4]. The depth of response including the assessment of MRD has emerged as one of the most relevant prognostic factors in patients with newly diagnosed MM (NDMM) as well as in relapsed/refractory (RR) disease. Indeed, reaching MRD negativity is associated with prolonged PFS and OS and may act as their surrogate according to the extensive number of clinical trials including meta-analyses in both NDMM and RRMM [5–7]. Importantly, in 2024, American Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved MRD negative complete remission (CR) as an early clinical endpoint for accelerated drug approval in MM which has been an unprecedented decision moving the whole field substantially forward. MRD seems to be an optimal guiding tool for management of the treatment in MM, for example, the fixed duration treatment with cessation of continuous therapy when MRD negativity achieved or vice versa, intensification, or change of therapy in the case of suboptimal response [8, 9].

According to IMWG updated response criteria, there are several MRD categories: (i) Flow MRD negative and (ii) sequencing MRD negative—both investigating the presence of clonal PCs within the BM; (iii) imaging MRD negative—evaluating the presence/activity of extramedullary/paramedullary disease outside of the BM using PET/CT, and (iv) sustained MRD negative—taking into account the component of “time” which has been proven to have a crucial impact on final outcomes of MM patients [10–13]. Currently, there are only two fully standardized techniques to assess MRD negativity: (a) Next generation flow cytometry (NGF) protocol developed by EuroFlow consortium reaching the limit of detection (LOD) to 10^{-6} (precisely 0.0002% recognizing 2 tumor PCs in 1 000 000 evaluated BM cells) [14], and (b) FDA-cleared next generation sequencing (NGS)-based MRD assay “ClonoSeq” by Adaptive technologies with LOD reaching also 10^{-6} . By the IMWG guidelines, the minimum sensitivity for both MRD assays (flow cytometry and NGS) must be 10^{-5} detecting 1 tumor plasma cell in 100 000 evaluated BM cells. It was demonstrated by many studies that both these techniques are highly biologically and clinically concordant [10, 15, 16]. However, in routine clinical practice, most institutions and laboratories worldwide typically use modified

in-house developed techniques, especially in the case of flow cytometry.

Majority of the data and knowledge generated in the field of MM MRD comes from clinical trials, and there are only limited data from real-world practice with sufficiently robust number of patients examined with adequate follow-up time [17, 18]. Here, we report the outcomes of 331 NDMM patients from 6 Czech hematological centers who underwent autologous stem cell transplantation (ASCT) and MRD assessment at Day +100 (D + 100) after ASCT using the flow cytometry method.

2 | Subjects and Methods

2.1 | Patients and Data Collection

In this retrospective, multicenter study, we aimed to identify transplant-eligible NDMM patients who underwent ASCT and had available MRD result using multiparameter flow cytometry at D + 100 after ASCT/before initiation of maintenance therapy using the data from the Czech Registry of Monoclonal Gammopathies (RMG). In total, we selected 331 patients diagnosed between September 2014 and January 2022 at six Czech hematological centers, Figure S1. Patients were treated in the real-world setting according to the institutional guidelines with standard triplet induction regimens followed by high-dose (HD) melphalan + ASCT +/- lenalidomide maintenance. Lenalidomide maintenance started to be reimbursed and routinely used in June 2020 and was administered in the following schedule: dose of 10 mg per day orally on days 1–21 on each 28-day cycle until progression or unacceptable toxicity. The MRD evaluation was performed at the fix time-point—approximately at D + 100 after ASCT and only patients reaching at least hematological partial remission (PR) were included in the analysis. High-risk cytogenetic abnormalities were defined at the time of diagnosis as the presence of at least one of the following: $t(4;14)$, $t(14;16)$, or $del(17p)$ determined by fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH). Clinical analysis was performed retrospectively based on data from RMG (<https://rmg.healthregistry.org/>). All patients signed written consent, and the study adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

2.2 | MRD Assessment

MRD was analyzed approximately at D + 100 after ASCT/before initiation of maintenance therapy at six different clinical flow cytometry laboratories, Table S1, Figure S1. MRD was evaluated using multiparameter flow cytometry from fresh BM aspirates collected in EDTA anticoagulated tubes and processed within 24 h. Each laboratory used its own approach including instrument, software for analysis, and antibody panel composition which are described in detail in Tables S2 and S3. Nevertheless, several common principles were followed to secure the harmonization of the results: (i) using at least 8-color panels; (ii) registration of the number of nucleated cells, and the LOD determined according to the formula, $(20/\text{viable nucleated cells}) \times 100$ [19, 20]; (iii) at least 1×10^6 nucleated cells were acquired for analysis and only samples with LOD in the 10^{-5} logarithmic

range were included. Briefly, all centers used antibodies against CD19, CD38, CD45, CD56, and CD138 to detect MRD, and five centers also included CD27 [14].

The gating strategy involved PC detection using a combination of CD38, CD138, and CD45 markers. Subsequently, the possible presence of clonal PCs was detected based on aberrant phenotype identified by antigen overexpression or underexpression compared to normal PCs (Figure S2). A detailed description of all antibodies, instruments, and software used is presented in Tables S2 and S3.

2.3 | Statistical Analyses

Kaplan Meier (KM) and log-rank test were used to assess PFS and OS from the landmark time (MRD assessment) until progression/death and death, respectively. Median follow-up was calculated using the reverse KM method. Significant differences between KM estimates were evaluated with log-rank and Mdir log-rank tests when KM curves crossed. Bonferroni correction was applied for multiple group comparisons. Hazard ratios (HR) were estimated with univariate Cox models, and multivariate analysis used Cox regression, including age, sex, International Staging System (ISS), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), cytogenetic risk, lenalidomide maintenance, and MRD status. Subgroup analysis was performed using PFS and Cox regression with Publish R package. The *p* value for interaction was obtained from a likelihood ratio test comparing the main regression analysis with the interaction model. The Pearson's Chi-squared, Fisher's exact, and Mann-Whitney U tests were used to statistically evaluate clinical differences between MRD positive and negative groups. All analyses were performed using R v4.2.3, survival v3.5.5, survminer v0.4.9, mdir.log-rank v0.0.4, readxl v1.4.2, tidyverse v2.0.0, and prodlim packages and ggplot2 v3.4.2 for plots that were manually adjusted with Inkscape v1.2. We used 0.05 as a significance threshold.

3 | Results

3.1 | Patient Characteristics and Therapies

A total of 331 NDMM patients achieving \geq PR after ASCT with available MRD results using multiparameter flow cytometry at D + 100 after ASCT were selected for the analysis. Patient characteristics at baseline are summarized in Table 1. Median age at the time of diagnosis of the entire cohort was 61 years (range: 34–71) and 53.5% (177/331) were male. Cytogenetics results were available in 54% (178/331) of patients and high-risk features were present in 21% (38/178) of them. Patients were treated according to routine clinical practice in the Czech Republic with standard induction regimens, majority \sim 75% (248/331) received combination of proteasome inhibitor (PI) and immunomodulatory drug (IMiD) and 18% (58/331) received PI-based regimen. All patients underwent single or tandem HD chemotherapy with ASCT; 81% (269/331) had full dose of melphalan 200 mg/m² and 11% (35/331) received the dose reduction with 140 mg/m² when clinically indicated. Regarding the maintenance therapy, lenalidomide was used in 28% (94/331) of patients. Overall, in this

selected population of MM patients; 52.3% (173/331) reached CR, 33.9% (112/331) VGPR, and 13.9% (46/331) PR evaluated at D + 100 after ASCT at the same time-point as MRD assessment. The median follow-up from MRD assessment was 30.7 months (IQR: 13.2–52.3) and the median PFS and OS for the entire cohort were 31.3 months and not reached with five-year OS rate of 66.3%, respectively.

3.2 | Outcomes Based on MRD Status and Hematological Response

MRD assessment was performed by 8-color multiparameter flow cytometry with median LOD of 0.001% (range: 0.0002%–0.0095%). MRD negativity was reached in 47% (157/331) of patients while 53% (174/331) of patients remained MRD positive at D + 100 after ASCT. Basic characteristics were mostly similar between the two groups; however, median age was slightly higher in MRD negative patients (63 vs. 60 years; *p* = 0.015) and the combination of PI and IMiD (VTD regimen) was used more frequently in MRD negative group (77.1% vs. 63.8%; *p* = 0.009). As expected, there were more patients reaching CR in MRD negative compared to MRD positive group (73.9% vs. 32.8%); on the contrary, very good partial response (VGPR) and PR were more frequent in MRD positive group (45.4% vs. 21%) and (21.8% vs. 5.1%), respectively; Table 1.

As anticipated, patients who achieved CR experienced significantly superior median PFS and OS versus patients reaching VGPR or PR (Figure 1A,B). Achieving MRD negativity at D + 100 after ASCT was associated with a significantly longer median PFS (49.2 months vs. 18.4 months; HR = 0.37; *p* < 0.001) with five-year PFS rates of 48% for MRD negative patients versus 18% for MRD positive (*p* < 0.001), (Figure 1C). MRD negativity was associated also with significantly better outcomes in OS (median not reached vs. 74.9 months; HR = 0.50; *p* = 0.007) with 5-year OS rates of 76% vs. 59% (*p* = 0.009), (Figure 1D). In patients reaching VGPR or better (*N* = 285), MRD negativity was again associated with significantly improved median PFS (not reached vs. 20.1 months; HR = 0.39; *p* < 0.001; five-year PFS rates of 50% vs. 21%, *p* < 0.001; Figure S3A) and OS (median not reached vs. 71.9 months; HR = 0.5; *p* = 0.013; five-year OS rates of 80% vs. 59%, *p* = 0.019; Figure S3B). Finally, if we considered only patients reaching CR (*N* = 173), MRD negative patients experienced significantly better median PFS (not reached vs. 23.7 months; HR = 0.36; *p* < 0.001; five-year PFS rates of 57% vs. 26%, *p* < 0.001; Figure S4A) and demonstrated improved median OS (not reached vs. 71.9 months; HR = 0.5; *p* < 0.001; five-year OS rates of 85% versus 71%, *p* = 0.12; Figure S4B) compared to MRD positive patients.

3.3 | Subgroup and Multivariate Analysis

The observed reduction in the risk of progression or death in the total population with MRD negativity was consistent across all patient subgroups including those with higher age (> 65 years; HR: 0.29), with ISS 3 stage (HR = 0.3) or with elevated LDH (HR = 0.37). Importantly, this benefit was even strongly pronounced in patients with high-risk cytogenetics (HR = 0.24) and was consistent in subgroup of patients reaching VGPR or better

TABLE 1 | Basic patient clinical characteristics by MRD status.

Baseline characteristic	N	According to MRD status			p ^a
		All (N = 331)	Positive (N = 174)	Negative (N = 157)	
Median follow-up from MRD assessment, mo (95% CI)			32.7 (14.3–52.9)	29.2 (12.6–52.5)	
Median age (range)		61 (34–71)	60 (41–71)	63 (34–71)	0.015
Sex, No. (%)					0.574
Male		177 (53.5)	90 (51.7)	87 (55.4)	
Female		154 (46.5)	84 (48.3)	70 (44.6)	
ISS stage, No. (%)	325				0.253
I		146 (44.9)	82 (47.7)	64 (41.8)	
II		85 (26.2)	47 (27.3)	38 (24.8)	
III		94 (28.9)	43 (25.0)	51 (33.3)	
LDH, No. (%)	329				0.429
Normal		266 (80.9)	144 (82.8)	122 (78.7)	
Elevated		63 (19.1)	30 (17.2)	33 (21.3)	
Cytogenetics, No. (%)	178				0.771
Standard risk		140 (78.7)	75 (77.3)	65 (80.2)	
High-risk		38 (21.3)	22 (22.7)	16 (19.8)	
Treatment, No. (%)					0.009
VTD		232 (70.1)	111 (63.8)	121 (77.1)	
VTD + Cyclophosphamide		16 (4.8)	13 (7.5)	3 (1.9)	
VCD		46 (13.9)	28 (16.1)	18 (11.5)	
PAD		12 (3.6)	10 (5.7)	2 (1.3)	
Different		25 (7.6)	12 (6.9)	13 (8.3)	
Melphalan, No. (%)	317				0.358
140 mg/m ²		35 (11.0)	20 (12.0)	15 (9.9)	
200 mg/m ²		269 (84.9)	137 (82.5)	132 (87.4)	
Different		13 (4.1)	9 (5.4)	4 (2.6)	
Clinical response, No. (%)					< 0.001
CR		173 (52.3)	57 (32.8)	116 (73.9)	
VGPR		112 (33.9)	79 (45.4)	33 (21.0)	
PR		46 (13.9)	38 (21.8)	8 (5.1)	
Lenalidomide maintenance					0.053
Yes		94 (28.4)	41 (23.6)	53 (33.8)	
No		237 (71.6)	133 (76.4)	104 (66.2)	

Note: N denotes number of patients with available data where N is different from 331.

Abbreviations: ISS, International Staging System; LDH, lactate dehydrogenase; PAD, Bortezomib + Doxorubicin + Dexamethasone; VCD, Bortezomib + Cyclophosphamide + Dexamethasone; VTD, Bortezomib + Thalidomide + Dexamethasone.

^aMann–Whitney test for age; Chi-Square test if no group has N < 5 otherwise Fisher exact test.

(HR = 0.39) or CR (HR = 0.35). The only subgroup of patients in which MRD negativity was not associated with improved PFS were those who received lenalidomide maintenance (HR = 1.06, $p = 0.895$); Figure 2.

Finally, in multivariate analysis only MRD positivity (HR = 2.537; $p = 0.003$), high-risk cytogenetics (HR = 3.31; $p < 0.001$), and the absence of lenalidomide maintenance (HR = 3.4; $p = 0.003$) emerged as independent adverse prognostic factors for PFS; Figure 3A.

FIGURE 1 | Kaplan–Meier estimates for (A) PFS and (B) OS according to hematological response: CR (red), VGPR (orange), PR (blue); and Kaplan–Meier estimates for (C) PFS and (D) OS according to MRD status: MRD negative (blue), MRD positive (red). HR: Hazard ratio calculated using MRD positive patients as the reference group.

3.4 | MRD Positive Patients Benefit From Lenalidomide Maintenance More Than MRD Negative

As emerged from subgroup analysis, receiving lenalidomide maintenance in MRD negative patients in our cohort was not associated with better PFS. Indeed, when we looked into MRD

negative patients, there was no significant difference in PFS between patients with ($N=53$) and without ($N=104$) lenalidomide maintenance ($p=0.747$). On the contrary, MRD positive patients substantially benefited from lenalidomide maintenance ($N=41$) which translated into improved 18-months PFS (81% vs. 46%; $HR=0.24$; $p=0.002$). In fact, MRD positive patients who received lenalidomide maintenance experienced comparable

FIGURE 2 | Subgroup analysis of progression-free survival (PFS) by various clinical and demographic factors, including age (≤ 65 vs. > 65), sex (female vs. male), International Staging System (ISS) stage (I, II, III), LDH level (normal vs. elevated), cytogenetic risk (standard vs. high-risk), depth of clinical response (VGPR or better vs. CR or better), and lenalidomide maintenance (yes vs. no). Hazard ratios (HR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) and *p* values are provided for each subgroup, with interactions evaluated between MRD status (negative vs. positive) and the listed variables.

FIGURE 3 | (A) Multivariable Cox regression analysis of PFS including age, sex, ISS stage, LDH level, cytogenetic risk, depth of clinical response, and lenalidomide maintenance, and (B) Kaplan–Meier estimates for PFS according to MRD status and presence/absence of lenalidomide maintenance: MRD negative patients with and without lenalidomide maintenance are depicted in light and dark blue, respectively; MRD positive patients with and without lenalidomide maintenance are depicted in light and dark red, respectively.

outcomes as MRD negative patients (with or without lenalidomide maintenance), Figure 3B. It is important to mention that median follow-up in patients receiving lenalidomide maintenance was shorter (13.1 months vs. 40.4 months) due to reimbursement rules in the Czech Republic; Table S4.

4 | Discussion

The depth of response including the assessment of MRD is a crucial prognostic factor in MM patients. Achieving MRD negativity is associated with improved PFS and OS which was demonstrated by many clinical trials including several meta-analyses [5–7, 21]. In 2024, the US FDA approved MRD negative CR as an early clinical endpoint for accelerated drug approval in MM, marking a milestone that will lead to faster approval of new agents and increased importance of MRD testing in other diseases. However, most current data come from clinical trials, with limited reliable real-world evidence available.

In our retrospective multicenter study of 331 transplant-eligible NDMM patients, we were able to recapitulate the outcomes of Munshi et al.'s meta-analysis. Achieving MRD negativity was associated with prolonged PFS (HR = 0.37; $p < 0.001$; Munshi et al.: HR = 0.33; $p < 0.001$). Median PFS was 49.2 months for MRD negative patients versus 18.4 months for MRD positive patients (meta-analysis: 61.0 months vs. 24.1 months). MRD negativity also significantly improved OS (our cohort: HR = 0.5; $p = 0.007$; Munshi et al.: HR = 0.5; $p < 0.001$). Numerically median OS was not reached for MRD negative patients and was 74.9 months for MRD positive patients; in meta-analysis, median OS was not reached versus 60.9 months. Finally, in our cohort, five-year OS rates were 76% versus 59% ($p = 0.009$) for MRD negative versus MRD positive patients and those in meta-analysis five-year OS rates were 70.9% and 50.5% ($p < 0.001$), respectively. Overall, our retrospective real-world study outcomes align with clinical trials. Real-world MRD data are limited, typically from single-center studies with fewer patients [18, 22, 23]. One of the largest real-world studies, published by Pasvolsky et al., focused on pre-transplant MRD assessment. It showed that pre-transplant MRD negativity is associated with better PFS, but not OS [17].

In most clinical trials, MRD results are reported for the intent-to-treat (ITT) population, meaning patients with active disease or missing MRD assessments are classified as MRD positive [24]. In our analysis, we selected only patients reaching at least PR at D + 100 after ASCT, and still the results in terms of HR are comparable and confirm strong prognostic value of MRD negativity. Currently, a key topic is whether MRD should be assessed only in patients reaching CR or also in those achieving VGPR. This debate is crucial given the FDA's recent approval of MRD negativity as an early clinical endpoint linked to CR, and the availability of novel immune therapies like CAR-T cells and bispecific antibodies, which can induce rapid, deep responses regardless of monoclonal immunoglobulin kinetics [10, 25]. Indeed, in our study, there was a substantial subset of MRD negative patients within the VGPR group (21%; 33/157) supporting the differentiation of standard hematological responses from MRD assessment. A similar proportion of MRD negative patients within the VGPR group was also reported by Pasquini et al. (21%; 49/244) [26].

We also showed that MRD negativity remains a strong prognostic factor in patients reaching VGPR or better and CR. Importantly, MRD negativity is associated with PFS improvements regardless of age, ISS stage, LDH level, or cytogenetic risk (Figure 2).

One of the open questions in the MM community is the management of maintenance therapy, including its optimal duration and the most effective combination. Lenalidomide monotherapy is the standard of care, though some countries are now using lenalidomide and daratumumab [27–29]. One of the suggested tools that might guide the cessation of maintenance therapy is MRD status. In our retrospective analysis, we took advantage of the fact that some patients received lenalidomide maintenance ($n = 94$) while the rest did not ($n = 237$). We demonstrated that MRD positive patients at D + 100 after ASCT benefited from lenalidomide maintenance and in fact had comparable outcomes as MRD negative patients (with or without lenalidomide maintenance). However, these results should be taken with caution as the median follow-up of patients receiving lenalidomide maintenance was shorter due to reimbursement rules (only 13.1 months). Despite the small number of patients on maintenance therapy and few events in this cohort, our results partially align with the UK Myeloma XI trial (Pawlyn et al. at ASH 2022), which suggests that MRD positive patients benefit more from lenalidomide maintenance than MRD negative ones. MRD positive patients should continue treatment until progression, while MRD negative patients may not benefit from continuous therapy beyond 2 to 3 years and might eventually stop treatment [30].

MRD assessment is an optimal tool for guiding and tailoring treatment in individual patients. The MRD-driven approach is likely the future or already in use at some myeloma centers. Many clinical trials (e.g., MASTER, MIDAS, REMNANT, MRD2STOP) are using MRD status for therapy decisions [8, 9]. Flow cytometry has become essential in MM management due to its simplicity, speed, and affordability. It is a crucial method for MRD assessment and quantifying circulating tumor plasma cells (CTCs), both important prognostic factors [31–34].

Regarding the future of MRD in MM, there are a few challenges that should be addressed. One of them is very likely the substitution of invasive BM aspirate by mini-invasive peripheral blood-based MRD monitoring. There are many possible approaches, such flow cytometry [35], mass spectrometry [36, 37], and also NGS [38]. Blood-based MRD monitoring should be accompanied by imaging techniques such as PET/CT to exclude extramedullary disease and reliably reflect the true MRD status [39–41].

We acknowledge the limitations of our study, including its retrospective nature, limited patient number and follow-up, and heterogeneous flow cytometry approaches for MRD assessment, so results should be interpreted cautiously. However, confirming clinical trial results in a real-world setting is valuable for physicians, patients, and regulatory authorities. This multicenter study supports the idea that achieving MRD negativity might allow discontinuation of lenalidomide maintenance without affecting survival measures, contrary to the current practice of therapy until progression, which is associated with cumulative adverse events and long-term toxicities.

Author Contributions

L.M., O.S., D.Z., R.H., and T.J. conceived and designed the study. L.M., O.S., D.Z. and T.J. wrote the manuscript. O.S., O.V., L.R., R.B., M.N., T.D. and T.J. analyzed flow cytometry data. D.Z. performed statistical analysis. T.S., T.P., H.P., L.P., M.S., J.M., V.L., A.J., J.S., M.S., V.R., V.M., J.R. and R.H. provided patients, study material and clinical or preclinical data. All authors interpreted and discussed the results. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript prior to submission.

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Ethics Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Consent

Clinical analysis was performed retrospectively based on data from RMG (<https://rmg.healthregistry.org/>) and all patients signed the written consent before entrance to the registry.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on the request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.